

LandSeaLot Deliverable 4.2

Comparisons and recommendations to LILs on low-cost technologies and potential and existing citizen science communities

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About this document

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ABSTRACT

This document presents the context of the LandSeaLot project Work Package 4 “increasing the observation capacity” and introduces the deliverable ambition. It explains the method followed to gather the information from the 9 LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LILs) and proposes an analysis of the information compiled as per month 9 in the project. Following the procurement procedure established in month 6, purchase of low-cost sensors will be performed in few stages, 2 essentially for the pieces of equipment costlier than 2000 Euros. Four LILs have purchase plans ready for the 1st phase.

1. Introduction

Coastal regions sustain large populations and economies. Most of the blue economy activities are in the Land-Sea Interface area (LSI), with conflicting interests between fisheries, aquaculture, energy production, sub-seabed gas storage, tourism, leisure and transport. A key question is how to reconcile the necessity for ecosystem restoration, biodiversity conservation and climate adaptation with the need to provide more energy, food, and bioresources from the sea. Addressing this question requires an enhanced understanding of the environment, which can only be provided by dedicated observation platforms across a range of 'use cases' encompassing the geographical, economic, and environmental conditions observed in Europe. The LSI represents one of the most challenging areas for comprehensive observations, due to their strong variability in space and time. This large variability requires a combination of different observational approaches in the LSI. Since significant economic activity is concentrated at the coastal and estuarine environments, they are surrounded by densely populated areas. This provides a largely untapped resource of communities invested in their environment, with the potential to grow citizen science initiatives, citizen understanding of coastal regions and calls-to-action, and thus increase the number and coverage of *in situ* observations.

The overarching objective of LandSeaLot is to bring together interdisciplinary capabilities to study the LSI which will be achieved through integrating and enhancing existing coastal observation efforts including *in situ*, satellite, modelling and citizen science.

LandSeaLot approach is developed at the European level and piloted in selected local regions in cooperation with local stakeholders: the LandSeaLot Integration Labs (LIL). These local studies will feed back experiences on feasibility and bottlenecks to the approach development.

Nine LILs in Europe have been selected to represent all European regional water bodies (Baltic, Mediterranean, and Black Seas, the North Sea and English Channel and the Atlantic coastal area). These include some of the most important riverine systems (Elbe, Rhine, Seine, Tagus, Rhone, Po, Evros, Danube), as well as deltas and estuaries, in a range of physical environments, from micro to macro tidal systems (Fig. 1). High priority societal challenges have been identified for each LIL and some initial activities plans have been envisioned to address one or more of these priorities. The plans will be adapted based on stakeholders' interactions and feedback.

One of the seven specific objectives of LandSeaLot is to expand the number of *in situ* observations using low-cost observation technology, such as specific, cheap but reliable sensors to be used via traditional scientific acquisition communities and/or citizen science engagement when applicable. The aim of LandSeaLot Work Package (WP) 4 is to expand observing capacity through implementation and piloting of low-cost technologies and exploitation of citizen science programs in the LILs.

WP4 will provide the LILs with technical solutions to collect new *in situ* observations to close observation gaps in the LSI to address some of their specific societal challenges. The technical solutions are composed of low-cost technologies and/or citizen science activities to collect the data. Where applicable, citizen science communities, such as boaters in marinas, will be engaged. WP4 strongly links to and is supported by WP6 "Data Management and Services" to guarantee an optimal and a long-term sustainable data flow to major data aggregators.

Figure 1: Distribution of the 9 LandSeaLot Integration Labs in Europe

At the inception of the project, WP4 framed the LILs societal challenges in terms of observation capabilities that could increase knowledge. D4.1 presented a summary of those technical and community needs and opportunities. In parallel, WP4 built a catalogue of low-cost technologies and communities (MS3) and a procurement procedure (MS4).

The present deliverable proposes to the LILs the first devices purchase plans to meet the LILs technological needs and the first list of citizen science communities to be activated for the LILs benefits.

2. Method

Late July 2024, WP4 reached the milestone MS3 "catalogue of low-cost technologies and communities". To be able to filter the content according to some criteria, the catalogue spreadsheet of low-cost devices was reworked. WP4 concentrated on the criterion cost, parameters and real time vs delayed mode.

On 30 August 2024, all LILs leads were asked to consult the [‘filtrable’ catalogue of sensors](#). They were asked to communicate to WP4 by 15 September 2024 the following info:

- What sensors do you think would be the most appropriate for deployment in ‘your’ LIL?
- How many sensors would be needed?
- Why these sensors?
- Who would deploy these sensors?
- What would be the 2nd best sensor for each sensor put forward? And why?

The LILs leads received a couple of reminders in September.

On its side, WP4 did the same exercise for each LIL based on the information featured in D4.1 "Summary of the technical and community needs of LILs". WP4 created a more visual, briefer version of the catalogue with only information about the name of the developer, the name of the

sensor, a photo of the sensor, the unit price and the parameters measured. An extract of the ‘visual’ catalogue is reported in Annex 1. This catalogue is a work in progress.

To confront the LIL leads findings and the WP4 findings about the most appropriate devices to deploy in the LILs and the citizen science initiatives or communities to activate, WP4 arranged telcons to discuss. To save some time, avoid telcon fatigue and because few LILs have similarities in their approach towards WP4 concept, group telcons were set up, composed as follow:

- North Aegean, Tagus, Firth of Forth LILs
- Wadden Sea, Baltic Sea, Danube Delta LILs
- Po Delta and Rhone LILs
- Seine estuary LIL

The same agenda was followed for the 4 interviews:

- purpose of the telcon (WP4)
- brief presentation of the purchase procurement by ETT (MS4 reached late July) and questions
- recollection of the outcome of D4.1 (WP4)
- update since D4.1 (LIL lead)
- discussion around WP4 and LIL leads findings with regards to sensors and citizen science actions, with the help of the ‘visual’ catalogue.

The telcons were recorded for internal purpose. The notes from the telcons were shared with the interviewees for comments and adjustments (Annex 2). Additionally, when appropriate, the sensors selections and related information were reported in [a spreadsheet](#) to access more rapidly the plans.

3. Results

The telcons were arranged with the leaders and key participants of the 9 LILs as listed in Table 1. They were conducted by SMHI with the participation of WP4 partners TEM, MARIS, ETT, SMHI and COVARTEC.

Table 1: Date and participants list of the LILs telcons

LIL interviewed	Interview date	Duration	Interviewed LIL partner	WP4 partners attending the interview
Seine Estuary and Bay	18 Sept 2024	1h	Ifremer	SMHI, TEM, COVARTEC, ETT, MARIS
North Aegean			HCMR	
Tagus and Sado estuaries System	23 Sept 2024	1h30	+ATLANTIC	SMHI, TEM, COVARTEC, ETT
Firth of Forth			University of Stirling	
Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta	30 Sept 2024	1h30	CNRS	SMHI, TEM, ETT, MARIS
Po Delta and North Adriatic			CNR	

Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary	30 Sept 2024	1h30	Deltares	SMHI, TEM, ETT, MARIS
Baltic Sea			SMHI	

The Danube delta and coastal area LIL was scheduled to have a telcon with the Wadden Sea and Baltic Sea LILs but due to previous engagement and last-minute commitment of GeoEcoMar, WP4 carried out the telcon without the Danube delta LIL.

The interviews notes and information from the purchase plans spreadsheet were compiled, analysed and summarised in the following 3 sections.

The summaries take into consideration the following 2 constraints:

1) the timing of the procurement procedure forces the LILs to have a priority order when purchasing devices. In brief, the procedure is divided in 2 types of purchases: the purchases with a total cost below 2000Euros and the ones above. For the purchases with a total cost below 2000Euros, the purchases can be performed directly at any time during the project and if possible, at maximum 2 separate moments. For the purchases with a total cost above 2000Euros, the purchases need to follow a 'Request For Quotation' (RFQ) procedure, i.e. the project will issue a call for a device type and companies will reply to the call and submit quotes for the project to consider. There will be few calls during the project, which dates are not determined yet.

2) one outcome of D4.1 concerning all the LILs was the need to evaluate and test the devices before a larger deployment.

Those 2 constraints considered, led to a 2-phase approach consisting of purchasing few units of devices, sometimes measuring the same parameters to compare their performances, to test them first and then once selected buying more units to be deployed more widely.

Additionally, some LILs needs changed between month 6 and 9 into the project, essentially due to the stakeholders' meetings. Some LILs have needs to low-cost sensors they did not have (Wadden Sea LIL and Baltic Sea LIL) and some have needs for different parameters (North Aegean LIL). The summaries also reflect those changes.

3.1. The LILs with no immediate purchase plans

The stakeholders of the Baltic Sea LIL (Swedish side) and of the Po delta LIL expressed interest in testing low-cost sensors. Therefore, WP4 will work on presenting a simplified sensor catalogue and use the outcomes from the first tests of the LILs who purchased sensors to test as soon as possible. Depending on the future interactions with the stakeholders in those LILs, purchasing sensors might be considered at a later stage.

The Gulf of Lions LIL needs of high accuracy pH and oxygen, which is difficult to meet with the sensors listed in the catalogue. Further investigation on the technological side is necessary and if any interesting sensor is identified, it might be purchase later.

The Firth of Forth LIL and Danube delta LIL showed interest in purchasing sensors, but at the time of the deliverable, WP4 is missing information to be able to present a possible purchase plan for those LILs. However, the work is in progress to reach possible purchase plans at a later stage.

3.2. The LILs with immediate purchase plans

Table 2 presents the LIL purchase plans of 4 LILs as per month 9.

An analysis from Table 2 shows that few similar devices are of interest for different LILs, such as the:

- **Autonomous conductivity/ temperature /depth/light /GPS sensor.**
The instrument is of interest for the North Aegean LIL, Wadden Sea LIL and the Seine LIL. The LILs are interested to test ‘very’ low-cost devices versus more sophisticated devices measuring the same parameters.
‘Very’ low-cost devices from Djup AB/Probe Fishing and 2DegreesC.
More sophisticated devices from Obscape BV, Fieldkit, SafetyNet Technologies Ltd and NKE Instrumentation.
- **isPEX phone-based reflectance from DDQ Pocket Science BV.**
The device is of interest to the North Aegean LIL and the Seine LIL.
- **Temperature loggers.**
Loggers are of interest to the Tagus and Sado LIL, the Wadden Sea LIL and the Seine LIL.
The company of interest is ElectricBlue.

Because of these common interests, WP4 will consider possible bulk purchases and redistributions of the devices to the LILs. This will be investigated within Task 4.5 by partner ETT. Furthermore, to save cost, efforts and to be efficient, an optimisation of the sensors testing could be proposed: one or two LILs could be testing all devices of interest for all the LILs interested and share the outcomes of the testing for instance. Finally, larger number of units could be purchased and then ‘lent’, circulated, rotated from one LIL to another. All those possibilities shall be discussed in the coming months by WP4 with the LILs concerned.

Table 2: LILs individual purchase plans for within 6 months/a year

Note: for the SEINE ESTUARY AND BAY LIL: The numbers in the column ‘quantity’ correspond to the number of units to be bought if the sensor is selected after the test of phase 1. Not all sensors will be purchased, nor in large numbers as listed.

LIL	Device type	Explanation	User	Quantity	Procedure	Comments
NORTH AEGEAN	Camera from e.g. HIKVISION	to count macroplastic flow for model validation	-Management Unit of Evros Delta -Demokritos University of Thrace	2 units minimum to cover large part if not entire width of the river	direct	1 unit in call 1
	Buoy from e.g. Element Works	To measure SSH, Chl-a, T, S, DO, TUR for the BGC model validation	-Fishermen -Management Unit of Evros Delta	2 units: 1 in estuary mouth, 1 in nearby coast	RFQ	1 unit in call 1

			-Demokritos University of Thrace			
	Portable turbidity/chl-a e.g. Chelsea Technologies Limited	To check the buoy data and have additional data points in other locations	Demokritos University of Thrace	1	RFQ	1 unit in call 1 Same sensor than in the buoy but different support platform
	Autonomous conductivity/depth sensor from e.g. Djup AB/Probe Fishing	Very low cost- 20 can be deployed in the river, river mouth and coast	-Fishermen -Management Unit of Evros Delta -Demokritos University of Thrace	20	direct	10 units in first 'small' purchase
	Autonomous conductivity sensor with higher accuracy from e.g. Obscape BV	1 higher cost/higher accuracy unit to field intercompare with the very low-cost units	-Management Unit of Evros Delta -Demokritos University of Thrace	2	RFQ	1 unit in call 1
	iSPEX phone-based	To test potential relationship to satellite or in situ products of chl-a	-Fishermen -Management Unit of Evros Delta -Demokritos University of Thrace	10	direct	4 units in first 'small' purchase
	Nets e.g. built by HCMR	To measure the microplastic flow- 4 points on the coast and 1 in the Evros river	-Fishermen -Management Unit of Evros Delta	5	direct	2 units in first 'small' purchase
TAGUS AND SADO ESTUARIES SYSTEM	Temperature loggers from e.g. ElectricBlue	To increase data coverage	7 potential stakeholders TBC (ports, foundation, aquafarms...)	50	direct	25 units in first 'small' purchase
	Mobile phone	To use with the loggers	scientist	1	direct	1 unit in first 'small' purchase
	Fixed station to measure water level from e.g. Coastal e-solutions	to contribute to the monitoring for the WFD	Portuguese Environment Agencies	4	RFQ or direct	TBD
WADDEN SEA, RHINE DELTA AND ELBE ESTUARY	Temperature loggers from e.g. ElectricBlue	To engage the canoers community	1 at NIOZ research inst. To test the quality 4 deployed by canoers	TBD	direct	5 units in first 'small' purchase

	Autonomous conductivity/ temperature /depth/light /GPS sensor from e.g. 2DegreesC	To fill the gap of data in shallow waters	1 at NIOZ pier to test the quality 1 with sailors and 1 with canoers to test the practicality	TBD	direct	3 units in first 'small' purchase to assess if more should be bought
	Cabled CTD type with various parameters sensors (incl. CDOM from e.g. NKE instrumentation)	To fill the gap of data in shallow waters and to compare results from more sophisticated device with the autonomous 'cheaper' ones	1 at NIOZ pier to test the quality 1 with sailors to test practicality	TBD	RFQ	2 units in call 1 to assess if more should be bought
SEINE ESTUARY AND BAY	Autonomous conductivity/ temp /depth sensor from e.g. Djup AB/Probe Fishing and 2DegreesC	For vertical profiling	-Sailors from 4 marinas -water agency staff -port staff -fishermen -divers -scientists	50	Direct	2 units of Djup AB and 1 of 2DegreesC in first 'small' purchase
	Autonomous conductivity/ temp /depth sensor from e.g. Fieldkit or SafetyNet Technologies Ltd	For vertical profiling	-Sailors from 4 marinas -water agency staff -port staff -fishermen -divers -scientists	About 10	RFQ	1 unit of Fieldkit and 1 unit of SafetyNet Technologies Ltd in call 1
	Temperature loggers from e.g. ElectricBlue	For point subsurface measurements or for moorings (e.g. caging)	-Sailors from 4 marinas -water agency staff -port staff -fishermen -divers -scientists	53	Direct	3 units in first 'small' purchase
	iSPEX phone-based	To possibly increase EO products quality	-Sailors from 4 marinas -water agency staff -port staff -fishermen -divers -scientists	50	Direct	2 units in first 'small' purchase
	Secchi disk from e.g. Brewtek	To measure turbidity	-Sailors from 4 marinas -water agency staff -port staff -fishermen -divers -scientists	50	Direct	1 unit in first 'small' purchase

3.3. Community activation

In D4.1, various citizen science initiatives and communities to activate were identified in almost every LILs (except in the Baltic Sea LIL). The LILs interactions with their stakeholders changed the situations for some LILs, such as the Wadden Sea LIL and the Baltic Sea LIL for which new communities would be activated. While for other LILs, such as the Gulf of Lions LIL, it is unlikely that the citizen science initiatives originally mentioned would be activated. Additionally, in some LILs the testing of the sensors will determine the citizen science initiatives and communities (or stakeholders) to activate, such as in the Seine LIL. An update has been drawn in table 3.

Table 3: Update on citizen science/community engagement in the LILs

LIL	Citizen Science/ community
BALTIC SEA	Swedish county administrative boards
FIRTH OF FORTH	No update on: Existing links with 2 communities associations that could serve as intermediaries: -Forth rivers trust -Scottish flood forum
GULF OF LIONS, RHONE DELTA	Astrolabe-Expeditions NGO is operating in Britany and will not be exported in the LIL.
NORTH AEGEAN	-Fishermen -Management Unit of Evros Delta -Demokritos University of Thrace
PO DELTA	Environment Protection Agencies
SEINE ESTUARY AND BAY	-Involving marinas as in citizen science initiative Phenomer -Sailors from 4 marinas -Water agency -Port of Rouen and Le Havre -Fishermen -Divers -Scientists
TAGUS AND SADO ESTUARIES SYSTEM	To be confirmed: -Port of Lisbon/FCUL -Gulbenkian Foundation -IPMA/ICNF -Troia Resort -CMCascais -Transtejo -Aquacultores Sado
WADDEN SEA, RHINE DELTA AND ELBE ESTUARY	-Sailors and canoers -No implementation of Phenomer concept to the LIL
DANUBE DELTA AND COASTAL AREA	No update on: -Remote villages communities

3.4. Take-home messages

Beyond the scope of this deliverable, the following 3 take-home messages were noted by WP4:

1-the procurement procedure:

As the procurement procedure and its timing are impacting the deployment strategies in the LILs, the September 2024 version of the procedure was briefly presented at the beginning of each telcon.

The presentation led to a lot of questions from the LILs leads, in particular from the leads interested in buying sensors. Each telcon and its questions helped improving the presentation at the next telcon (and the procedure version), as questions from one LIL are likely to be relevant to other LILs. Rich of this experience, WP4 decided to produce a Frequently Asked Questions (FAQ) document based on the 4 sets of discussion around the procurement procedure. It was also proposed to present to all the LILs, via telcon or video tutorial (format to be determined) in detail the procurement procedure and facilitate as much as possible this often tedious and challenging exercise. These suggestions will be considered by ETT as part of Task 4.5.

2- the catalogue:

While using the catalogue of sensors, it became obvious for WP4 partners and LIL leads that the catalogue was difficult to use in its current form, despite the useful and rich information it contains. Every sensor in the catalogue shall be scrutinized to assess if the sensor should be considered cost-efficient or not, how the sensor shall be deployed, etc. Categories shall be selected to facilitate the navigation through the list (fixed versus mobile station, stuck to a platform versus actively lowered down in the water, with or without cable...) to give a better idea of the deployment methods for instance.

3- sensors exchange across LILs:

As seen in the analysis of table 2, some same sensors are of interest for different LILs. Therefore, it might be valuable for the LILs to exchange sensors, in particular for the costliest ones. Tasks 4.5 and 4.2 will assess the feasibility of such an approach, supported by the LILs concerned. In any case, to facilitate collaboration between the LILs, purchase and deployment plans will be updated regularly and shared with all LILs. More interviews are not yet planned but WP4 is considering having a telcon with the LILs who will get sensors before the end of 2024 to address this point.

4. Conclusions

- 4 LILs have a purchase plan ready for phase 1. However further discussions will take place to increase efficiency in purchasing instruments, to facilitate testing of sensors and to encourage exchange across LILs.
- For purchase beyond phase 1 and for interactions with few LILs stakeholders, additional consideration will be given to the catalogue of low-cost technology to improve its navigability. Categorisation and visualisation will be introduced.
- An in-depth procurement procedure description to the LILs will be prepared along with an FAQ document.

Annex 1. Extract of the ‘visual’ catalogue of low-cost technology

Developer	Photo device	Name device	Price (EUR)	Parameters
2DegreesC CS initiatives		2°C Wavelet	450	Conductivity Temperature Depth (Pressure) Light (Luminous Flux) Geoposition (GPS) Time (GPS+RTC) Acceleration
Atlas Scientific		Conductivity K 1.0 Kit	212	Conductivity (µS/cm) Total dissolved solids (ppm) Salinity (PSU) (ppt) 0.00 – 42.00 Specific gravity (sea water only) = 1.00 – 1.300
Water Insight BV		WISPstation Validation report exists from H2020 EOMORES	3500	<u>Water quality based on the colour of the surface water:</u> Incoming sky radiance, Upwelling water radiance, Downwelling hemispherical Irradiance, Remote sensing reflectance, Chl-a , TSM, CDOM, CPC, Cyanochlorophyll, biomass cyanobacteria, Optical water type, water colour as Forel-Ule index, KdPAR and Kd490, Secchi disk depth , Euphotic depth, Trophic state
Chelsea Technologies Limited		TriLux 2 models of fluorometer for freshwater and marine To integrate to something	3150	chlorophyll, turbidity and algal pigments
nke instrumentation		WiSens 6 models depending on parameters	3500	<u>autonomous data logger</u> -T and pressure -T, Pressure, dissolved oxygen -T, pressure and Chl-a -conductivity, pressure and temperature - turbidity, pressure and temperature -temperature and pressure for assessing waves or tides

		<p>WiMo (4 sensor locations)</p> <p>WiMo+ (7 sensor locations)</p>	5500	<p>Default param: T and pressure</p> <p>Then can be added:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -conductivity -turbidity -oxygen -Chl-a -algal pigments -CDOM -pH -Nitrate -Ammonium
Djup AB / PROBE fishing		PROBE	140	<p>Water temperature</p> <p>Depth</p> <p>Conductivity</p> <p>Light</p> <p>Acceleration</p>
SafetyNet Technologies Ltd		<p>SeaSensor</p> <p>For fisherman</p>	7000	<p>Depth / Temp / Turbidity / Light intensity / Motion</p>
NEOTEK		<p>MASTODON -</p> <p>Lightweight benthic platform for sediment-water interface monitoring - Programmable and recoverable</p>	3800	<p>Dissolved Oxygen / Turbidity / temperature & others (Sensors not included)</p>
		<p>NEOB500 -</p> <p>Lightweight Energy Buoy for real-time surface monitoring</p>	7700	<p>For multi-parameter probes (w/ conductivity / temperature / Dissolved Oxygen / Turbidity / temperature) & others- probes and sensors not included</p>
FieldKit		<p>FieldKit Underwater</p>	2325	<p>Pressure</p> <p>temperature</p> <p>dissolved oxygen,</p> <p>pH,</p> <p>conductivity,</p> <p>external temperature,</p> <p>oxidation reduction potential on-board</p>
Obscape B.V		<p>Radar Wave Gauge</p>	3000	<p>Hm0, Hmax,</p> <p>Tp, Tm01, Tm02, Tm-10, Tavg, Tmax,</p> <p>water level,</p>

		Radar Level Gauge	2500	Water level
Coastal-e Solutions		Water level ultra Tide/River gauge	990	Water level (m)
		Wave gauge	1450	high-frequency water level
Sofar Ocean Technologies		Spotter	5500	Surface: Waves, SST, atmospheric pressure, wind (inferred). Subsurface: temperature, water level , currents.

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Annex 2. Minutes from the 4 telcons with the LILs

LIL Seine Estuary and Bay interview

with Ifremer on 18 Sept 2024

Other partners present: SMHI, TEM, COVARTEC, ETT, MARIS

Interview video recorded for internal purposes only.

Goal of the telcon: getting closer to a purchase plan

Output will contribute to deliverable D4.2 *Comparisons and recommendations to LILs on low-cost technologies and potential and existing citizen science communities* in M9

Points of discussion:

-procurement procedure

-discussion on SC/communities

-discussion on sensors:

What parameters

what sensors,

how many,

the costs,

which ones can go via direct procedure when. Which ones go via quotation process when

Rationale for the sensors

Alternatives

If many sensors, we need a priority order.

MINUTES

-presentation of the procurement procedure by ETT

What LILs have to do

Direct assignment procedure

Each LIL has a total budget of 2'000€ allocated for small purchases, allowing for a maximum of 2 purchases. Interested LILs must provide a purchase request to the Procurement Manager on LIL's letterhead at purchases@landsealot.eu that includes:

- **Cost-effective technologies of interest:** this includes a list of cost-effective technologies required for procurement, which may vary in type or category;
- **Details of sellers:** information specifying the sellers who will supply the cost-effective technologies, including their contact details and other relevant information;
- **Offer submission:** the offer(s) from the seller(s) must be submitted on behalf of ETT S.p.A. and must address the specific requirements. This ensures that all necessary information and terms are included in the offers for evaluation and procurement consideration.

Information required from the seller:

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • General description of the cost-effective technologies; • Detailed technical features and specifications of the cost-effective technologies; • Indication of the cost-effective technology's lifetime; • Terms regarding the cost of purchase; • Terms regarding the procurement lead time; • Terms regarding transportation, including cost and time; 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Terms regarding payment methods and schedules; • Terms regarding warranty coverage; • Terms regarding annual maintenance, including cost, time, and type of maintenance required; • Terms regarding possible interventions in case of breakage or malfunction, including cost, time, and type of intervention; • Operational cost.
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Ifremer questions:

1-this is a lot of info requested for a few hundred euros devices. Is ETT assisting in getting that info? And if some info is not there, is it a deal breaker?
A lot of info is already in the catalogue.

2-some devices are interesting from a cost point of view and also because they are easy to be deployed by citizens, however they are not classic scientific equipment, so they need to be tested. Being limited to 2 purchases/items might be tricky, especially if we need to test the sensors.

The 2 purchases refer to 2 times to buy, i.e. different sensors from different sellers can be bought at one moment, twice during the project duration any time. The total purchase should be below 2k Euros.

The direct procedure is always open, during the whole project.

Some LILs might be interested by the same sensors, perhaps the same pool of sensors could be lent from one LIL to another.

Ifremer question: will there be a complete list of the sensors that all the LILs will purchase? In order for each LIL to see what the others will have and deploy and try to be as synergetic as possible between LILs.

--> **Once WP4 has all the list of sensors from the 9 LILs, which will compose D4.2, it will be circulated to all LILs.**

Sometime should be allocated during the LSL week for discussion between LILs on how to best use the LSL pool of sensors (exchange of test, lending options...)

What LILs have to do

Procurement procedure via RFQ

1. **Submission to Procurement Manager:** the LIL compiles the form available on the LandSeaLot webpage with a list of the necessary cost-effective technologies, specifying requirements outlined in chapter 6.1 Information required from the LIL;
2. **Publication of RFQ**
3. **Submission of offers**
4. **Evaluation by evaluation committee**
5. **Outcome communication**
6. **Purchase completion:** upon selection, the Procurement Manager completes the purchase within 30 days, arranging for the cost-effective technologies to be shipped directly to the LIL at the specified address provided during the submission to Procurement Manager step;
7. **Delivery acknowledgement:** upon receiving the purchase cost-effective technologies, the LIL must promptly send a receipt of delivery acknowledgement to the Procurement Manager via purchases@landsealot.eu.

Information required from the LIL at the time of request submission →

- General description of the cost-effective technology
- Technical specifications of the cost-effective technology
- Quantity
- Procurement lead time
- Shipping details (recipient's name and address)

-With regard to the CS activities and communities, SMHI reminded all about information we shared during the March 2024 interview:

--> Phytoplankton bloom dynamics, sediment fluxes and morphological evolutions and habitat modifications are the topics of interest.

--> The LIL is interested in extending a citizen science initiative for alerting and identifying blooms and to engage citizens in a collective low-cost observation strategy.

--> Marinas could be acting as citizen scientists.

--> An existing project (Phenomer) will be 'elevated' in 2 ways: with the integration of a new community (marina) and adding cost-effective sensors.

The following update was shared:

TEM asked if there were any other activities than Phenomer in which the marinas could be involved. Ifremer knows only Phenomer for now (info: Ifremer has a contact person for Phenomer in the Seine LIL, and is back from leave).

About the marinas engagement, TEM and Ifremer had an interesting discussion with someone from Le Havre marina about involving the sailors from Le Havre marina in collecting measurements. He asked for more info about the sensors to deploy, his interest depends on this too. This is why testing the devices is important.

Furthermore, there are more marinas along the coast of the Bay of Seine, not only le Havre, a key question is also how they could be involved. To be attractive, we need to go to them. We need to select good sensors that provide good info for the LIL and then present the selection to the marinas (and possibly other communities such as sailors and divers groups).

Additionally, from the LIL stakeholders interaction, it came out that some are already taking measurements for their own needs and would be interested in using LC sensors.

This would ensure good coverage.

The proposed plan is in phase 1 to select some sensors for different parameters of interest, buy them in 2024 and evaluate them and learn how to manipulate in 2025, then to present them to the various groups of volunteers to show how they can help and ask them which ones they can deploy and in phase 2 assess how many of each device is needed and purchase the ones that will be deployed for one or 2 years.

With regard to parameters, in the interview in March 2024, the following parameters were mentioned as of interest:

-fluorescence and chlorophyll-a

-temperature, salinity and turbidity (good for sediments dynamics and morphology) (Secchi disk optical turbidity sensors for turbidity?)

-nutrients (from KoM)

-PML radiometers Ispex

Ifremer personal to conduct the measure and analysis

SMHI presented the '[photo catalogue of sensors](#)' under construction, a more visual catalogue, and a list of potential sensors from the catalogue fitting perhaps the parameters. This list should be confronted with Ifremer list when it will be available.

--> for water color, Chl-a--> Water Insight BV

--> chl a + other bio param--> Chelsea Technologies Limited ,

--> chl a + T, S, turbidity, conduc, pH, 2 different options, buoy/logger -->nke instrumentation (3.5-5.5kE)

--> turbidity, T--> Probe (100E), SafetyNet Technologies Ltd (7kE), NEOTEK (4k –12kE)

--> Nut--> Clear Water Sensors (20kE per nut) NOT LOW COST

For Ifremer, priority criterias are:

- what is the sensor, the parameter provided

- is it stand alone, self-contained? Do we need to buy something else for it to run or does it run by itself?

- how easy is it to be used?

Accuracy questions come after.

ACTION: Ifremer will check the catalogue and put forward some devices for each param of interest, along with a justification of the use and information of who might deploy them. The number of units needs to be informed too. A priority listing might also be useful.

To consider with regard to numbers: balance act

It was noted that the number of sensors to be purchased and deployed will depend on: the unit cost and the assistance needed. If a large number of devices is deployed, the need for assistance might be high after the end of the project too. This needs to be considered.

'Train the trainers' should be considered.

It also might be that it is easier to deploy some sensors first quickly to establish the working process with the communities and engagement. And then introduce later a sensor of higher interest for the LIL. A balance act will have to be observed.

It was concluded that starting to engage one marina is a good start.

The list of sensors of interest was received post interview and is [here](#).

3 LILs interview: Tagus and Sado estuaries System, North Aegean, Firth of Forth

With +ATLANTIC, HCMR, University of Stirling on 23Sept 2024

Other partners present: SMHI, TEM, COVARTEC, ETT

Interview video recorded for internal purposes only.

Goal of the telcon: getting closer to a purchase plan

Output will contribute to deliverable D4.2 *Comparisons and recommendations to LILs on low-cost technologies and potential and existing citizen science communities* in M9

Points of discussion,

-Procurement procedure (ETT)

-Discussion on CS

-Discussion on sensors:

What parameters

what sensors,

how many,

the costs,

which ones can go via direct procedure when. Which ones go via quotation process when

Rationale for the sensors

Alternatives

If many sensors, we need a priority order.

MINUTES

-presentation of the procurement procedure by ETT

Questions

HCMR: Can Small purchases be done to sellers outside of Italy, EU? Yes, from anywhere in the world

Can the 2 times purchase be done the same year? Yes, anytime.

+ATLANTIC: When will be the 2 calls for the 'More expensive purchase'? There are no dates yet set for those but once the procurement is fully finalised (still missing legal info), the dates will be set and the first will be as soon as possible.

About the use of the maintenance budget, the process needs to be established. Who receives the bill, who pays the bill... Additionally, the maintenance for water level devices if bought from a company remote from the deployment location, it could end up being very costly. Perhaps the remote company should be asked if they have for instance a local person of contact for

maintenance or shipping of broken pieces. Maintenance and replacement (e.g. vandalism) is an important point in the purchase procedure.

If there is a need to buy 2 devices of 1500EU each, can they be bought separately via small purchases procedure? It could be considered bad practice to split the bills.

The small purchase can start now.

University of Stirling: Who receives the devices? It is shipped directly to the buyer.

Who is the legal owner? ETT but the lifetime of the devices bought should be of the project duration. Depreciation will be asked to the sellers. +ATLANTIC suggested to set up a 'loan for 100 years' contract, the device he wishes to buy has a 15 years lifetime. The legal department of Deltares.

What about the liability? Who is liable? There will be a contract between ETT, the receiver of the device and the LIL leader to sign, including an indemnity clause.

What budget should cover the data charges associated with telemetry, the SIM cards needed for example? ETT mentioned that the cost should likely be included in the purchase of the device by the developer (not as a maintenance cost). ETT will add a note that this needs to be asked to the developer upon purchase.

Does the LIL have to purchase devices only from the catalogue? The instruments purchased by ETT for the LIL do NOT have to be in the catalogue, the catalogue is to help finding devices. If a LIL wishes to purchase a sensor not listed in the catalogue, the device will be added to the list.

HCMR: In 2k EUR, the VAT is included.

For the 'More expensive purchase', is it possible for the LIL to submit a quote on behalf of the company? Some big companies might not take the time to reply to the call, while the quote can be obtained online. ETT needs to consult ETT legal department.

HCMR added that indeed some commercial companies might not bother if one unit is purchased, so if the same devices is interesting for few LILs, then it might be interesting to buy in one go few devices to the company and distribute them. ETT shall look into the practicality.

Installation cost should be included in the 2000EUR or in the quote. It is not included in the maintenance budget.

-SMHI presented the table below. It is a reminder all about information we shared during the March and May 2024 interview with regard to CS/communities and the parameters/low-cost devices of interest. In addition, in the table, it is proposed some devices from the catalogue to stimulate discussion and confront with the input from each LIL leads. Each column presents the info for one LIL.

SMHI also presented the '[photo catalogue of sensors](#)' under construction, a more visual catalogue, and a list of potential sensors from the catalogue fitting perhaps the parameters.

	Tagus and Sado	North Aegean	Firth of Forth
Promising CS/communities mentioned in March-May 2024 interviews	aquaculture producers Portuguese environmental Agency Portuguese Association of Ports and Marinas Port of Lisbon (blue flag in FOCCUS, monitoring needed)	fishermen and/or sailors -REMEDIES, Cyclades demonstration site -Plastic Pirates: Go Europe	Scottish flood forum Some groups from the forum already work with river tracks sensors Forth rivers trust
Devices suggested by WP4 for discussion:	Cost-efficient tech needs mentioned in March-May 2024 interviews		

<p>Water level</p> <p>If out of water: -Ocean Origo AB (UP1 - Water level monitoring system- real time) -Obscape B.V (2 devices, near real time) -Coastal-e Solutions (2 devices near real time)</p>	<p>Flooding: -water level For the rivers and for the tides around the estuaries, contribution to the monitoring for WFD of the Portuguese environmental Agency -->For the river 2 real time? --> for the tide 2 near real time</p>	<p>Water level in river: Under the bridge one</p>	<p>low-cost water level: sensors mentioned in the LIL description but not much discussed in the March 2024 interview.</p> <p>Priority for the LIL</p>
<p>Temperature</p> <p>SafetyNet Technologies Ltd (not small loggers) ElectricBlue</p>	<p>Heat wave: --> temperature for Port of Lisbon (blue flag in FOCCUS, monitoring needed) AND aquaculture producers --> Electric Blue CRL --> 50-100? If it does pressure too it would be helpful.</p>		<p>monitoring data gaps : water temperature (measurement frequency not high enough across the catchment), Turbidity and conductivity, water quality, freshwater biodiversity, blue carbon...</p>
<p>Chl, turbidity</p> <p>Coastal-e Solutions Obscape B.V NEOTEK</p>		<p>L-C Buoys: Real time very important L-C buoy from Elements Community, to be tested in the LIL: Number: 2 Includes temperature sensor and GPS.Sensors to be added: -chl-a -turbidity -oxygen -conductivity -portable TUR/FLU sensor</p>	
<p>Camera</p> <p>SafetyNet Technologies Ltd MarineSitu Obscape B.V</p>	<p>Needs for 6 units in D4.1 but for what?</p>	<p>macroplastics flow: camera under bridges --> 2 testing done by HCMR with a camera in another river.</p> <p>High resolution is important.</p>	
<p>Net</p>		<p>microplastics flow: -->net--> 5, build by HCMR. Those will be deployed by fishermen and/or sailors --> camera if any available</p>	
<p>Varia</p>		<p>Conductivity, came from stakeholders, 20 units, coverage Ispex</p>	<p>Test bed: Forth ERA</p>
<p>Additional parameters of interest, extract from D4.1</p>	<p>-pressure (logger type) -salinity -nutrients</p>	<p>IN RIVER: -water level</p>	<p>-Water temperature -Water quality -freshwater biodiversity</p>

- chlorophyll	-Nutrient	-carbon -turbidity -conductivity
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The following update were shared:

HCMR mentioned that following the stakeholder meeting they had, the priorities changed, and the North Aegean LIL is no longer interested to acquire a cost-effective sensor that measures water level, they can have access to the existing data. The stakeholders are more interested in having conductivity sensors. There are also 2 more stakeholders, the local university and the Management Unit of the Ministry of Environment & Energy that manages the National Park of Evros river.

HCMR shared a spreadsheet about the requirements that the LIL NA compiled in preparation for the telcon. The document contains columns listing the instruments, the explanations for what the devices are needed, the quantity needed, and 2 additional columns labelled phase 1 and 2 which correspond to the 2 purchase times for equipment costing. These columns give an idea of the priorities which in the NA LIL is essentially to start with the testing of at least one instrument for each of the parameters/topic.

An updated version (including a column on the users/deployers) of the table above, post interview, is available on the SharePoint [here](#) and below:

Instrument	explanation	Stakeholder/Citizen user	Total units	Phase1	Phase2
For MACROplastics Camera (e.g. HIKVISION 4MP Motorized Varifocal Bullet Solar Power 4G Network Camera Kit)	used to force the particle circulation model. 2 units minimum to cover large part if not entire width of the river (+potentially also for satellite data ground truthing). Low cost of maintenance	.-Management Unit of Evros Delta .-Demokritos University of Thrace	2	1	1
Buoys (SSH, Chla, T, S, +DO, +TUR) e.g. Element Works (including anchoring structures purchase, installation, spare parts for service for the buoys)	Circulation model and BGC model forcing and validation. Satellite SSH, SST, SSS, Tur, Chla ground truthing. CMEMS O2 reanalysis model evaluation. 2 units: 1 in estuary mouth, 1 in nearby coast Real time data to be incorporated to POSEIDON data flow Low cost of maintenance	.-Fishermen .-Management Unit of Evros Delta .-Demokritos University of Thrace	2	1	1

Portable tur/Chla (! Same sensor as in Buoys+Portable data logger) e.g. Chelsea	Check of buoys Chla sensor operation, additional Chla points, Satellite Chla data ground truthing Near Real time data (transmitted "manually") Easy deploy, easy of use, no maintenance	.-Demokritos University of Thrace	1	1	0
Conductivity+depth sensor VERY low cost, autonomous e.g. PROBE FISHING , adjustable sampling interval?	Circulation model validation. Satellite SSS ground truthing. 20 low-cost units to cover river, river mouth and coast 1 higher cost units for field intercomparison with lower cost units Easy deploy, ease of use, low cost of maintenance	.-Fishermen .-Management Unit of Evros Delta .-Demokritos University of Thrace	20	10	10
Conductivity sensor HIGH accuracy, autonomous (obscape CT station?)	intercomparison with lower cost units Easy deploy, ease of use, low cost of maintenance	.-Management Unit of Evros Delta .-Demokritos University of Thrace	2	1	1
iSPEX phone-based	To test potential relationship to satellite or in situ products of chlorophyll-a, then if successful to increase Chla in situ points Easy deploy, easy of use, low cost of maintenance	.-Fishermen .-Management Unit of Evros Delta .-Demokritos University of Thrace	10	4	6
NETS for MICROplastics	Close to the coast in 4 points (e.g. near the delta, near a city water discharge and 2 control areas) to allow the validation of the particle circulation model and 1 in the Evros river to capture the flow. Easy deploy, ease of use, low cost of maintenance	.-Fishermen .-Management Unit of Evros Delta	5	2	3

Conductivity and salinity are parameters requested by modellers and stakeholders, the LIL NA agreed on the measurement strategy, in this case to deploy a swarm of very low-cost sensors and one higher cost sensor for field intercomparison. The LIL NA welcome suggestions of devices models from WP4 and other LILs, if they deploy some.

Tagus LIL has not originally planned to measure conductivity, but they have an upcoming meeting with stakeholders that could be influential in what to purchase and deploy. In general stakeholders are keen on have conductivity measurements if they are reliable.

NA, Tagus and Wadden Sea LILs shall collaborate to test conductivity sensors and perhaps exchange them.

At the time of the interview, FoF and Tagus LILs did not share their views on the sensors catalogue and proposed devices to deploy. They will share their input afterwards via email.

Note post interview: Info for the Tagus LIL were received and are [here](#).

General questions:

Is there a strategy to use the same sensors in different LILs?

It has been discussed but there is no strong decision on it. For time sake, a compromise might be needed, e.g. to start with some sensors and then in parallel to test some others.

All LILs will have access of what each LIL is planning to purchase and deploy, in order to facilitate collaboration.

More interviews are not planned before end of October 2024 but it could be considered to have a telcon with the LILs who will get sensors before the end of 2024 in order for all LILs to know what the others are doing with regard to sensors and communities.

2 LILs interview: Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta, and Po Delta and North Adriatic

with CNRS, CNR on 30 Sept 2024

Other partners present: SMHI, TEM, ETT, MARIS

Interview video recorded for internal purposes only.

Goal of the telcon: getting closer to a purchase plan

Output will contribute to deliverable D4.2 *Comparisons and recommendations to LILs on low-cost technologies and potential and existing citizen science communities* in M9

Points of discussion,

-Procurement procedure (ETT)

-Discussion on CS

-Discussion on sensors:

What parameters

what sensors,

how many,

the costs,

which ones can go via direct procedure when. Which ones go via quotation process when

Rationale for the sensors

Alternatives

If many sensors, we need a priority order.

MINUTES

-presentation of the procurement procedure by ETT

-SMHI presented the table below. It is a reminder all about information we shared during the March and May 2024 interview with regard to CS/communities and the parameters/low-cost devices of interest. In addition, in the table, it is proposed some devices from the catalogue to stimulate discussion and confront with the input from each LIL leads. Each column presents the info for one LIL.

SMHI also presented the ‘[photo catalogue of sensors](#)’ under construction, a more visual catalogue, and a list of potential sensors from the catalogue fitting perhaps the parameters.

	Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta	Po Delta and North Adriatic
CS/communities	Via RIOMar project: -Astrolabe-Expeditions, NGO and partner, sailing boats measure temperature and salinity with self-built sensors. Opportunity to export the activity from Britany to the LIL -Biodiversity French Agency, public agency, could serve as link to communities	Citizen science initiatives existing are not relevant for the LIL activities.
Cost-efficient tech	-Salinity via the Astrolabe-Expeditions, SensOcean programme but they build their own so no buy from our end? There are low cost sensors already deployed in this LIL via the project RIOMar (MAstodon, YUCO from Seaber	Not planned (the LIL is well monitored from a coverage point of view. If any additional measurements were to be set up, high accuracy would be interesting and required)
Parameters of interest, extract from D4.1	-salinity -fluorescence -oxygen -pH--> both to be used to reconstruct pCO2 via neural network. Priority?	-salinity in the last 30km of the mouth inland (saltwater intrusion) -Salinity in the river measured at the bottom. For the saltwater intrusion is needed. -carbon --> Carbon monitoring in the river is missing -water level, wave height in the coastal area (storm surge and flooding) --> later in the project.

Po delta, North Adriatic:

CNR informed that during summer sensors (radiometer, WISP station) from the catalogue were purchased via other projects funding. The outcome of the testing could be shared with LandSeaLot and the LILs interested in the device.

Some of the local stakeholders (Environment Protection Agencies) mentioned during the LIL-stakeholders interactions, that they would be open to testing and trying some sensors, if the opportunity presents itself.

Conclusion is that: For now, there will be no sensor purchased for the Po delta, North Adriatic LIL. Though WP4 will work on developing a version of the catalogue fit for interaction with local stakeholders and a process on how to share this version to further discuss and engage with them.

Gulf of Lions, Rhone delta:

The efficiency and accuracy of some sensors are important in the LIL. The stakeholders do not have expertise with sensors, and they would not be the right persons to select and choose one for the LIL, the scientists know better the place and what the needs are. pH and oxygen are the big gaps in the LIL and only one sensor from the catalogue would be of interest, but it is rather not a low cost one. However, LIL are not restricted to buying sensors from the catalogue, they can decide to buy a cost-efficient sensor which is not (yet) on the list.

With regard to activating CS project, deployment of more Mastodon moorings would be more

interesting for the LIL than trying to have the Astrolabe-Expeditions operating their SensOcean programme in the LIL location (currently they operate in Brittany, not in the Gulf of Lions).

2 LILs interview: Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary and Baltic Sea

with SMHI and Deltares on 30 Sept 2024

Other partners present: SMHI, TEM, ETT, MARIS

Excused: Hereon, GeoEcoMar

GeoEcoMar being absent from the discussion, Danube delta and coastal area LIL input was not collected.

Interview video recorded for internal purposes only.

Goal of the telcon: getting closer to a purchase plan

Output will contribute to deliverable D4.2 *Comparisons and recommendations to LILs on low-cost technologies and potential and existing citizen science communities* in M9

Points of discussion,

-Purchase procedure (ETT)

-Discussion on CS

-Discussion on sensors:

What parameters

what sensors,

how many,

the costs,

which ones can go via direct procedure when. Which ones go via quotation process when

Rationale for the sensors

Alternatives

If many sensors, we need a priority order.

MINUTES

-presentation of the procurement procedure by ETT

An FAQ on the purchase procurement will be produced and shared with the LILs.

For the procurement process we need to check what is the best approach in cases where a sensor is of interest for a few LILs. Who will approach the developer, LIL, ETT or WP4.

Deltares: When will the 2 calls be? ETT replied that the 1st call will likely be set in Nov, as soon as possible.

-SMHI presented the '[photo catalogue of sensors](#)' under construction, a more visual catalogue, and a list of potential sensors from the catalogue fitting perhaps the parameters.

SMHI added that a LIL can decide to buy a sensor which is not in the catalogue MS3 reached in July 2024 and shared with the LILs.

-SMHI presented the table below. It is a reminder all about information we shared during the March and May 2024 interview with regard to CS/communities and the parameters/low-cost devices of interest. In addition, in the table, it is proposed some LIL devices from the catalogue to stimulate discussion and confront with the input from each LIL leads. Each column presents the info for one LIL.

	<u>Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary</u>	<u>Baltic Sea</u>
CS/communities	-SOOP -Implementation of Phenomer concept to the LIL	Not the priority interest of the LIL. Community and citizen science landscape has not been assessed prior to the interview.
Cost-efficient tech	Not planned	Not planned (high accuracy is required)
Parameters of interest, extract from D4.1	-pH -carbon	IN RIVER: -turbidity -discharge -water level -nutrients -carbon

Baltic Sea LIL:

SMHI mentioned that as shared during the interview in May 2024 to collect the LILs needs, the Baltic Sea LIL was not interested in deploying low-cost sensors and activating any CS initiatives or communities. However, at the 1st stakeholder meeting in June 2024 for the Swedish side of the Baltic Sea, the participants showed a strong interest towards low-cost sensors. The topic of interest from Swedish stakeholders are brownification and connection between carbon (dissolved organic matter) and nutrients, as well as turbidity, with a management perspective.

At this stage, no sensor has been identified. The Baltic Sea LIL, Swedish side, will continue to look into what sensors would be of interest, deployed by who, where, how many etc...

Wadden Sea, Rhine delta and Elbe Estuary:

Deltares shared updates that took place since the May 2024 interview:

- Deltares had contact with a group of sailors and canoers motivated to become citizen scientists and take sensors on board.

-In parallel, the NIOZ in Texel agreed that we test the sensors alongside their traditional in-situ instruments to assess the quality.

-Some progress was made in the analysis of the system too: pH and pCO₂ were mentioned at first as variables of interest, however they are not parameters suitable for CS, so the list of variables has been extended. Additionally, there is a lack of in-situ observations in shallow areas. The Wadden Sea is a system of deep gullies and drying tidal flats, in which a lot of biology is happening. Salinity, turbidity and ideally oxygen data are needed in those shallow areas close to the coast.

Furthermore, as sensors should be attached to a ship or lower from a ship or canoe, the LIL needs 'mobile' sensors.

With all this in mind, Deltares put forward the following sensors from the catalogue to

discuss:

- WiSens and WiMo from NKE instrumentation
- netH2O from Elements Works
- 2°C Wavelet from 2DegreesC
- NEOB500 from NEOTEK

Temperature: After a brief discussion on **temperature loggers**, it was mentioned that a first small purchase of few data loggers would be ideal to engage the canoers into citizen science, due to the easy to use feature of the sensor (loggers are activated with a mobile phone via an app and deactivated with a contact with the phone). Temperature is not a main interest parameter, but the data could be used in validation of temperature models.

Chl-a:

The LIL has satellite data for chl-a but no validation data in the shallow parts where there is reflection by the sediments, where one may doubt the satellite data.

The Phenomer concept (mentioned in the Seine LIL) was thought to be implemented in the area. Labs are needed for this. More discussion is needed in order to assess if the concept can be put in place in the LIL. Discussion with Ifremer will take place.

Note post telcon: Deltares and Ifremer discussed about Phenomer. Following this conversation, the LIL decided to not pursue the idea to implement the Phenomer concept to the Dutch coast. The reasons are as follow:

In France, the labs partners with Phenomer inspect the water samples with a microscope.

For the LIL, the interest is to have samples analysed to get chl-a measurements for satellite validation, for that the samples would have to be filtered, frozen in the same way to be analysed by one lab. Additionally, the samples should be taken when the satellite overpass them. The set up is then different from the Phenomer one and setting up a new concept is out of the LIL scope.

Collaboration with the SOOP project:

A tube to encase sensor (currently working with an Atlas Scientific sensor) has been developed within SOOP. It can be attached to a boat. Other sensors could possibly fit in the tube. Trilux from Chelsea Technologies Limited from the catalogue needs to be encased. This needs to be further discussed.

Discussion around Deltares's sensors suggestions from the LSL catalogue:

-2°CWavelet from 2DegreesC: The device seems to be in development still. It is to be attached to something (e.g. diving bottle). 2DegreesC is a US CS initiative using the sensor, developed by a Swedish company. A discussion needs to take place with the developer. It would be interesting to test the sensor.

3 units could be purchased to be located on a NIOZ pier for testing the quality, and on sailing ship and canoe to test the practicality.

This device is very comparable with the Probe device, in terms of parameters. The specifications between the two devices need to be scrutinized.

-WiSens and WiMo from NKE instrumentation: they are more advanced devices.

Interesting to test as it measures chl-a. The device is connected to something. Advanced sophisticated device, this is not CS friendly. It could be in a marina or with reliable sailors lower with care. Attaching them to a buoy used to mark shipping lanes (outcome of stakeholder meeting) is not an option here because of the fouling in those not too deep waters.

WiSens is simpler than WiMo, for WiMo additional sensors can be added. Discussion with the developer to know what prices and what is in it etc needs to take place.

Specification, such as if this device needs to be incased (compatibility with SOOP project to be investigated).

Ideally, the NKE devices should be received in March/April 2025 for having time to present the results of the test at their meeting in June 2025.

It could be a cross LIL one, because CDOM is interesting for other LIL, such as the Baltic LIL.

2 devices: one for the quality testing and one for the deployment testing

- NEOB500 from NEOTEK and neth2O from Elements Works are only buoys, without sensors. Therefore, they are not interesting anymore.